

Ethnobotanical Studies of Medicinal Plants from Marathwada effectively used on Rheumatism

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Abstract:

Rheumatism is a chronic disease which is progressive and systemic in nature. It is characterized by inflammation of joints, damaging cartilage and bone around the joints. It leads rheumatoid nodules, eye inflammation, cardio pulmonary diseases. To avoid hazardous effects of allopathic medicines it is possible to use the medicinal plants in various forms in order to cure Rheumatism. Medicinal herbs have been traditionally a resource for the treatment of many diseases. There are many medicinal plants that have shown anti-rheumatoid properties. The present work is focused on the ethnobotanical studies on medicinal plants from Marathwada region which are effectively used to cure Rheumatism.

Keywords: Ethnobotanical, Rheumatism, Chronic Joints, Medicinal Plants, Marathwada.

Introduction:

Rheumatism is a chronic disease which is progressive and systemic in nature. It is characterized by inflammation of joints, damaging cartilage and bone around the joints. It leads rheumatoid nodules, eye inflammation, cardio pulmonary diseases (Amandeep kaur *et al*, 2012). Medicinal herbs have been traditionally a resource for the treatment of many diseases (Zarei GA, *et al*, 2015; Baharvand-Ahmadi, B., *et al*, 2015, Mahmoudi GA, *et al*, 2016, Rezvanirad A, *et al*, 2016, Bahmani, M., *et al*, 2016). Treatment of inflammatory diseases, such as rheumatoid arthritis is practiced based on traditional medicine in many countries (Peter A. Akah and Alphonsus I. Nwambie, 1994).

Rheumatism is a common problem today, particularly in old people. It is generally cured using allopathic medicines. Allopathic medicines apart from curing disease cause many hazardous side effects on biological system of human beings. Alternatively, there are many medicinal

plants that have shown anti rheumatoid properties. The present study is focused on the medicinal plants from Marathwada region which are effectively used to cure Rheumatism.

Marathwada (70° 5' - 78° 5' E Longitude and 17° 5' - 20° 5' N Latitude) a geographical region of the [Indian state](#) of [Maharashtra](#). Marathwada has total area of 64590 km². Districts of Marathwada region are Chatrapati Sambhajinagar, Nanded, Latur, Parbhani, Jalna, Beed, Dharashiv, Hingoli. Marathwada is divided into tropical dry deciduous forests, open scrub jungles and vast tracks of grasslands according to vegetation. There are more than 1650 species of Angiospermic plants in Marathwada of which more than 500 species are medicinally useful (Naik, 1998). It is found that 61 species of flowering plants which are useful on Rheumatism.

Methodology:

The present study is based on survey of flowering plants used on Rheumatism in Marathwada during 2023-2025. The plants were identified with the help of Flora of Marathwada-V. N. Naik (1998). The medicinal value of plants was verified with the knowledge of local people, aged rural folks, traditional ayurvedic practitioners, local herbal drug sellers and referring literature of Naik (1998), Trivedi (2003-2008), Gambhire (2008), Mali and Bhadane

(2011), Mohmmad Nafees Iqbal and Suradkar (2011), Lal and Singh (2012), Bhogaonkar and Ahmad (2012), Nag and Hasan (2013), Muley and Sharma (2013), Biradar (2013).

Results and Discussion:

Study revealed that there are 61 species of flowering plants from Marathwada which are useful on Rheumatism. The results are tabulated in the form of botanical name, family, local name and parts used to cure Rheumatism.

Sr. No.	Botanical name	Family	Local/Vernacular name
01	<i>Adhatoda zeylanica</i>	Acanthaceae	Adulsa
02	<i>Alangium salviifolium</i>	Cornaceae	Ankol
03	<i>Allium cepa</i>	Amaryllidaceae	Kanda
04	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Amaryllidaceae	Lasun
05	<i>Aloe vera</i>	Asphodelaceae	Korphad
06	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>	Apocynaceae	Satvin
07	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Asparagaceae	Shatavari
08	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>	Plantaginaceae	Brahmi
09	<i>Brassica juncea</i>	Brassicaceae	Mohari
10	<i>Cadaba fruticosa</i>	Capparaceae	Habab
11	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>	Asclepiadaceae	Rui/ Ruchaki
12	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	Cannabaceae	Ganja
13	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i>	Sapindaceae	Kapalphodi
14	<i>Carthamus tinctorius</i>	Asteraceae	Kardi
15	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Caesalpinaceae	Bahava
16	<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i>	Celastraceae	Malkangni
17	<i>Chrysopogon zizanioides</i>	Poaceae	Wala
18	<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i>	Cucurbitaceae	Indrayan
19	<i>Citrus limon</i>	Rutaceae	Limbu
20	<i>Crataeva nurvala</i>	Capparidaceae	Vayvarna
21	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	Poaceae	Gavati Chaha
22	<i>Drimia indica</i>	Asparagaceae	Rankanda
23	<i>Erythrina variegata</i>	Fabaceae	Pangra
24	<i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Tridhari nivdung
25	<i>Gossypium herbaceum</i>	Malvaceae	Kapus
26	<i>Grewia tiliifolia</i>	Malvaceae	Dhaman
27	<i>Guizotia abyssinica</i>	Asteraceae	Karal

28	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>	Periplocaceae	Anantmul, Kavli
29	<i>Holarrhena antidysenterica</i>	Apocynaceae	Bhuiringani
30	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i>	Apocynaceae	Pandhra Kuda
31	<i>Hygrophila auriculata</i>	Acanthaceae	Kolsunda
32	<i>Lepidium sativum</i>	Brassicaceae	Ahaliv
33	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>	Sapotaceae	Moha
34	<i>Magnolia champaca</i>	Magnoliaceae	Sonchafa
35	<i>Mentha piperita</i>	Lamiaceae	Pudina
36	<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Cucurbitaceae	Karale
37	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Moringaceae	Shevga
38	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i>	Nyctanthaceae	Parijatak
39	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i>	Lamiaceae	Tulas
40	<i>Operculina turpethum</i>	Convolvulaceae	Nishottar
41	<i>Papaver somniferum</i>	Papaveraceae	Afu
42	<i>Piper nigrum</i>	Piperaceae	Mire
43	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	Plumbaginaceae	Chitrak
44	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	Fabaceae	Karanj
45	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	Portulacaceae	Ghol
46	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Erand
47	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	Poaceae	Gahu
48	<i>Salvadora persica</i>	Salvadoraceae	Pilu/Mithijar
49	<i>Sapindus mukorossi</i>	Sapindaceae	Reetha
50	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i>	Anacardiaceae	Bibba
51	<i>Senna alexandrina</i>	Fabaceae	Sonamukhi
52	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	Solanaceae	Kamoni
53	<i>Soymida febrifuga</i>	Meliaceae	Rohan
54	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Combretaceae	Hirda
55	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	Menispermaceae	Gulvel
56	<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>	Apiaceae	Ova
57	<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i>	Fabaceae	Methi
58	<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Verbenaceae	Nirgundi
59	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Vitaceae	Draksha
60	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Solanaceae	Ashwagandha
61	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Zingiberaceae	Ale

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